

frequency factor and the entropy of activation for cyclohexanone and *m*-methyl cyclohexanone given in Table 3 confirm the bimolecularity of the reaction³.

TABLE 3—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERE FOR THE ENOLIZATION OF CYCLOHEXANONE AND *m*-METHYL CYCLOHEXANONE

(Glycine) <i>M</i>	Cyclohexanone		ΔS^\ddagger e. u.
	E (K. cal. mole ⁻¹)	A min. ⁻¹	
1.2	22.80	2.303×10^{12}	- 4.112
1.6	20.52	8.824×10^{10}	- 10.51
2.0	20.52	1.390×10^{11}	- 9.60
	<i>m</i> -methylcyclohexanone		
1.2	19.61	7.70×10^8	- 17.83
1.6	22.80	1.15×10^{11}	- 06.66
2.0	22.80	1.13×10^{11}	- 05.14

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF DIELECTRIC CONSTANT

% of solvent (v/v)	Cyclohexanone		<i>m</i> -methyl cyclohexanone <i>k</i> , $\times 10^8$	
	(Dioxan)	Methanol	Ethanol	Dioxan
5.00	4.77 *	2.50	2.76	2.98
10.00	4.44 *	2.49	2.74	2.90
15.00	3.80 *	2.38	2.70	2.80
20.00	3.12 *	2.20	2.66	2.73
25.00	2.88 *	2.10	2.65	2.50

*Rate coefficients of cyclohexanone at 35°.

To study the solvent effect the enolization studies have been made in 0.8 *M* glycine and 0.01 *M* substrate at 35° in different methanol, ethanol and dioxane water mixtures. The lowering of rates (Table 4) with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium indicate that the enolization of the ketones is due to dispersion of charge in the transition state since the reactive species is expected to be the conjugate acid species of the corresponding cyclic ketone. The reaction via either molecularity (uni or bi) will involve dispersion of charge in the transition state thereby lowering the rate only to a slight extent by a change over from medium of low to high ionising power.

The experimental results discussed above lead to the similar mechanism of acid catalysed enolization as given for cyclopentanone³.

The rate of enolization of cyclohexanone has been found to be higher as compared to that of cyclopentanone³ in presence of glycine. The substituent methyl in 3-methyl cyclohexanone reduces the rate of

enolization but its rate is still higher than that of cyclopentanone. The difference in reactivity of cyclopentanone and cyclohexanone may be attributed to the difference in ring strains⁴, during the enol formation, since enolization could involve in shifting of exo-double bond to the double bond in the ring demanding two carbon atoms (instead of one) to have SP² configuration. The lowering of rate in 3-methyl cyclohexanone may be due to the reduced hyperconjugation and steric hindrance offered by methyl group to the incoming water molecule to bring about the reaction bimolecularity.

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Potentiometric Studies of Some Bivalent Metal Chelates of 2-Hydroxy-3-Isopropyl-6-Methylbenzaldehyde

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COMPLEXATION equilibria of metal complexes of UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Co^{2+} with 2-hydroxy-3-isopropyl-6-methylbenzaldehyde(I) have been studied potentiometrically. The stability constants of these chelates were determined in 75:25 per cent (v/v) dioxane-water medium by Calvin-Bjerrum titration technique¹ at $25^\circ \pm 0.1$ maintaining ionic strength 0.1*M*. The order of the stability of chelates was $\text{UO}_2^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$.

A study of stabilities of (I) with bivalent metal ions was carried out for the first time. Garg and Pande², alone, have reported stability constants of a few bivalent metal chelates of *o*-thymolaldehyde. They³ had also discovered that *o*-thymol aldo-semicarbazone forms soluble deep coloured complexes of Fe^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , VO^{2+} and UO_2^{2+} and insoluble ones Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ce^{2+} and Pd^{2+} .

Present communication reports successive stability constants of complexes of (I) with various bivalent metals determined potentiometrically by using Irving-Rossotti method⁴.

Experimental

The ligand (I) was synthesized⁵ in the laboratory. All chemicals used were A. R. grade except perchloric acid (E. Merck, G. R. Grade) and ligand. Dioxane used for the experimental work was purified⁶. The stock solutions of NaClO_4 , HClO_4 and NaOH were prepared in the usual manner in the double distilled water. All metal perchlorate solutions except UO_2^{2+} were standardized complexometrically by EDTA titrations⁷. UO_2^{2+} was estimated gravimetrically as U_3O_8 ⁸.

A precision research pH-meter, the Corning Model 12, with a wide range glass electrode-calomel electrode system was used. The pH meter was calibrated at 25° using two buffers. Following solutions were titrated separately against standard NaOH ($1.04M$) potentiometrically at $25^\circ \pm 0.1$: (i) free HClO_4 , (ii) free HClO_4 + ligand and (iii) metal perchlorate in free HClO_4 + ligand. The ratio between the metal and the ligand was kept 1:4 and the ionic strength $0.1M$ was maintained with appropriate amount of $0.64M$ NaClO_4 solution. The titrations were carried out at an inert atmosphere by bubbling oxygen free nitrogen through the solutions.

The values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated employing experimental method of Irving and Rossotti⁴. The appropriate corrections for the H^+ concentrations have been made as per the work of Irving and Mahnot⁹ and the values have been accordingly modified. Appropriate ion corrections were made at high pH.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves of solutions (i) and (ii) \bar{n}_A values at various pH values were calculated. The formation curve was plotted between \bar{n}_A and pH extending over a range $0.31 > \bar{n}_A > 0.91$ (Fig. 1). This indicates the formation of species HL only. The value of pK_1^H was evaluated from the half integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$.

From the straight line plot of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \right]$ against pH, also the pK_1^H was determined. This value agrees well with that obtained by half integral method. The plots are excluded for the sake of brevity.

Fig. 1. Proton Ligand Formation Curves.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii) \bar{n} and pL values were calculated. The plots \bar{n} values against the corresponding pL values were acquired to get the formation curves of the metal complexation equilibria (Fig. 2). From these, the stability constants, $\log K_1$

Fig. 2. Metal-Ligand Formation Curves.

and $\log K_2$ were evaluated corresponding to pL values at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and $\bar{n} = 1.5$ respectively. A plot of $\log \frac{\bar{n}/1 - \bar{n}}{\bar{n}}$ against pL , for different metal systems, was drawn to evaluate $\log K_1$ values. Again the plots are not cited for economy of space. The values obtained by both these methods are in excellent agreement. Moreover, the least square method was also practised to obtain $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ in the case of UO_2^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} . The limit of error for $\log K$ values was ± 0.05 and the standard deviation ± 0.06 ¹⁰. The most representative values are recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Cation	H ⁺	UO ₂ ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Mg ²⁺
log K ₁	11.40	9.60	8.83	8.45	7.87	7.81	7.72	5.63
log K ₂	—	8.84	7.27	—	6.76	—	—	—

For H⁺, K₁ corresponds to the species LH, while for metal ion K₁ and K₂ correspond to species ML and ML₂ respectively.

The metal ligand titration curve was found to be well separated from the titration curve which indicates that the liberation of proton from the phenolic 'OH' group is due to chelation.

The stability constants of metal complexes of this ligand fall in the order UO₂²⁺ > Cu²⁺ > Zn²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Cd²⁺ > Mg²⁺, in agreement with the Irving-Williams order¹¹.

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Some New Antifungal Triazolyl Sulphides

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3-Amino-1,2,4-triazole (Amizole) is a commercial herbicide. Many compounds having triazole ring have been reported to exhibit fungicidal^{1,2}, insecticidal^{3,4} and pesticidal^{5,6} properties. The SH group attached

to the heterocyclic nucleus may enhance the fungicidal⁷ activity. The sulphides have been reported to be more biologically active than parent mercapto compounds⁸. Further, heterocyclic sulphides have been known to possess significant antifungal⁹ activity. Pesticidal activity of bis (4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl) alkanes has revealed that activity increased¹⁰ with the increase of number of methylene groups. In view of this, the above title compounds have been synthesised to study their antifungal activity.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected.

Aryloxyacetyl hydrazines :

These were prepared by the method of Conti¹¹.

1-Aryloxyacetyl-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides¹² :

These were prepared by the reaction of aryloxyacetyl hydrazines and arylisothiocyanates.

3-Aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles¹³ :

These have been prepared by alkaline cyclisation of corresponding thiosemicarbazides.

Bis-(3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-disulphides(I) :

To an ice-cold ethanolic solution (25 ml) of 3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (0.01M), a cold ethanolic solution (25 ml) of bromine (0.005M) was added dropwise with swirling. The precipitate thus obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and recrystallised. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 1.

Bis-(3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-1,2,4-triazol-5-yl)-ethylene disulphides(II) :

To an ethanolic solution (20 ml) of 3-aryloxymethyl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (0.01M), sodium acetate (2.0 g) and ethylene dibromide (0.005M) were added. The contents were refluxed for 4 hrs and then poured into water. The solid separating was filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are listed in Table 2.

Fungicidal activity :

All the eighteen compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity against *A. flavus* and *A. niger* by agar plate technique^{13,14} at three different concentrations namely 1:1,000, 1:10,000 and 1:100,000. All the compounds possess moderate fungicidal activity.

In general, compounds having chlorine or methoxy group were found to show higher antifungal activity. The ethylene disulphides were much better than the corresponding sulphides with respect to their fungicidal